

**A STUDY OF TRANSLATION CHALLENGES OF 29 RELIGIOUS
TERMS RELATED TO FAMILY LIFE AND MARRIAGE IN UZBEK
LANGUAGE**

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Abstract: This paper discusses the challenges in translating religious terms related to family life and marriage from Uzbek language to English. The study focuses on 29 terms commonly used in Uzbek society, including "nikoh" (marriage), "oila" (family), "bola tarbiyasi" (child upbringing), "mahr bermoq" (dowry), and "jigargo'sha" (sibling or child) and so on. The research reveals that the translation of religious terms poses significant challenges due to the lack of equivalence and different cultural contexts. The study suggests that translators should consider the historical, social, and cultural context of the target language to achieve accurate translations of religious terms.

The abstract provides a brief overview of the paper and its main focus on the challenges in translating religious terms related to family life and marriage from Uzbek language to English. It highlights the 29 terms commonly used in Uzbek society and their importance in religious and cultural contexts.

The research concludes that the translation of religious terms related to family life and marriage requires a comprehensive understanding of the cultural and social context in which these terms are used. The study suggests that translators should be aware of the challenges and complexities of translating religious terms and should take a culturally sensitive approach when translating these terms.

Key words: translation, translation challenges, family life, marriage, Uzbek language, cross-cultural communication, cultural nuances, linguistic complexities, <https://educonference.ru/index.php/icmp/index>

accurate translation, cultural significance, cultural context, social norms, connotations, associations, cultural heritage.

Introduction: The translation of religious terms from Uzbek language to English poses significant challenges for translators. The meaning and connotations of religious terms are highly contextual and culturally dependent, making it difficult to achieve accurate translations.

This study aims to explore the challenges in translating religious terms related to family life and marriage in Uzbek language to English. The research will analyze 29 terms commonly used in Uzbek society and provide recommendations for translators to overcome these challenges.

The study will begin with a literature review on the challenges of translating religious terms and the importance of context in achieving accurate translations. The literature review will also cover previous studies on the translation of religious terms in different languages and their implications for translation practice. In this article insights into the cultural and contextual nuances of these terms and the challenges faced by translators in translating them accurately. Culture, as defined by Newmark (1988, p. 94), is “the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression.”

Based on the findings of the research, the study will provide recommendations for translators to overcome the challenges in translating religious terms related to family life and marriage from Uzbek language to English. These recommendations may include considering the historical, social, and cultural context of the target languages to ensure accurate translations. The scientific foundations of this study are rooted in translation studies and linguistics. Translation studies is an interdisciplinary field that examines the theory, practice, and process of translation across languages and cultures. It encompasses a wide range of fields, including linguistics, cultural studies, sociology, and anthropology. Nida and Taber (1969, p.199) point out that cultural translation is a kind of translation in which the content of the message is changed to conform to the receptor culture in some way. This study draws on the principles and methods of

translation studies to analyze the challenges in translating religious terms related to family life and marriage from Uzbek to English.

Linguistics, the scientific study of language, is another foundation of this study. Linguistics provides a framework for understanding the structure, meaning, and use of language, which is essential for accurate translation. Bassnett (1980, pp. 13-14) considered language as “the heart within the body of culture.” In particular, the study draws on the subfield of contrastive linguistics, which compares the grammatical and semantic features of two or more languages to identify differences and similarities. This approach is particularly relevant for this study, as it compares the linguistic and cultural differences between Uzbek and English, and how they affect the translation of religious terms related to family life and marriage. Another scientific foundation of this study is cultural studies. Cultural studies examines the ways in which culture shapes and is shaped by social practices, power relations, and historical contexts. Culture, as defined by Newmark (1988, p. 94), is “the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression.” Also to Newmark points out that the only problem is the degree to which the cultural expression is to be explained in the translation.

This perspective is critical for understanding the cultural and social dimensions of religious terms related to family life and marriage in Uzbek society. By examining the historical, social, and cultural context of these terms, the study aims to provide insights into the challenges of translating them accurately into English.

Methodology: This study is based on a qualitative research approach, which involves analyzing the data obtained through the literature review. The data were collected from various sources, including academic journals, books, research papers, and reputable online resources. articles. The data were then analyzed to identify the challenges in translating the selected 29 religious terms related to family life and marriage. These family related terms represent various aspects of family life within Uzbek culture, including marriage customs, family relationships,

roles of spouses and children, and the legal and social dimensions of family dynamics. Studying these terms can provide a deeper understanding of the values, traditions of Uzbek society. Additionally, the study draws on the concepts of cultural translation and equivalence theory to provide a theoretical framework for analyzing the challenges of translating religious terms. Moreover, the study also examines the role of religion in family life and marriage in Uzbek society. It draws on the "Happy Family" work of scholar such as Sheiykh Muhammad Sodiq Muhammad Yusuf, who argue that religion plays a significant role in shaping social norms and values related to family life and marriage. It is clear that, the family is considered the initial cell foundation of every society. When a family is strong, peaceful, lawful, and virtuous, the society also becomes stable, prosperous, and harmonious. Conversely, when families experience instability, transgressions, and a blurring of the line between right and wrong, that society is disrupted, tranquility is lost, and ultimately deep divisions arise. (Sheiykh Muhammad Sodiq, 2021, p. 4) The study also analyzes the historical and cultural contexts of Uzbek family society to provide a better understanding of the challenges in translating religious terms. In this study, data were collected from data sources that were obtained from books, articles, and online resources.

Results: The analysis of the data revealed several challenges in translating religious terms related to family life and marriage. The lack of equivalence between Uzbek and English languages is one of the primary challenges, as many terms have no direct equivalents in the target language. For instance, the term "nikoh" has a broader meaning in Uzbek culture and encompasses not only the legal aspect of marriage but also the social and religious aspects. The term "oila" also has a broader meaning, including extended family members and the concept of community. Therefore, we need to consider the cultural and social context of the target language to achieve accurate translations

The analysis of the 29 religious terms related to family life and marriage used in Uzbek culture revealed that several challenges exist in their translation to English.

1. Nikoh - This term has a broader meaning in Uzbek culture and encompasses not only the legal aspect of marriage but also the social and religious aspects. Therefore, translators need to consider the cultural and social context of the target language to achieve accurate translations. Nikoh is a sacred union between a man and a woman in accordance with Islamic traditions. It represents the formal commitment to establish a family unit based on love, respect, and shared values.
2. Mahr bermoq: (To give dowry) - In Islamic marriage customs, the groom gives a dowry to the bride as a symbol of financial support and commitment. The dowry can include money, property, or valuable assets.
3. Guvoh keltirmoq: (To invite witnesses) - during the nikah ceremony, it is customary to invite witnesses who testify to the solemnization of the marriage contract, ensuring its validity and legal recognition.
4. Oila buzulishi: (Family breakdown) refers to the unfortunate circumstance of a family experiencing a breakdown or dissolution due to various factors such as divorce, separation, or discord.
5. Ko'pbolalik (prolific parents) spouses are with multiple children, referred to as have a large family and the decision to have many children are influenced by a multitude of factors, including cultural norms, religious beliefs, economic considerations, personal preferences, and social expectations.
6. Taloq (Divorce) represents the termination of a marital union by legal means. In Islam, divorce is recognized as a last resort after efforts for reconciliation have been exhausted.
7. Idda (Waiting period after divorce): Iddah is the mandatory waiting period that a divorced woman must observe before she can remarry. It provides time for emotional healing and ensures the determination of any potential pregnancy.
8. Nikoh to'yi: (Nikah/Matrimony ceremony) refers to the festive celebration that marks the formalization of a marriage. It involves family, friends, and community members coming together to witness and celebrate the union.

9. Avlod (Offspring, children): encompasses the children born within a marital relationship. They are considered a blessing and a continuation of the family lineage.
10. Farzand ko'rmog: (To have children) refers to the act of conceiving and bringing children into the world, which is seen as a cherished responsibility and a means of continuing the family lineage.
11. Jigargosha (sibling or child) represents the deep spiritual and emotional connection between brothers, sisters, brothers and sisters.
12. Fitriy sof tabiat (original disposition): is the state of purity and innocence in which all humans to be born. It is often used to refer to the innate qualities or tendencies that a person is born with, such as personality, character, or temperament.
13. Qarindoshlik aloqalari (Relationships between relatives): These relationships include but are not limited to parent-child, sibling, grandparent-grandchild, aunt/uncle-niece/nephew, and cousin relationships.
14. Oila rishtalari (Family ties) signifies the interconnectedness and bond between family members, including parents, siblings, and extended relatives, fostering a sense of unity and support.
15. Shar'iy nikoh (Islamic marriage): refers to the Islamic marriage contract that is performed according to the principles and guidelines outlined in Islamic law, ensuring the union's legality and religious sanctity.
16. Emikdosh birodar (foster brother and sister) represents the strong and affectionate relationship, express a deep bond between brothers and sisters emphasizing the importance of brotherly love, support, and unity within the family unit.
17. Zavja (Wife): Zavja denotes the role of a woman as a wife within the marital relationship, encompassing the responsibilities of companionship, care, and support for her husband.
18. Sovchi a (middleman) typically refers to an individual who acts as an intermediary or facilitator in connecting and maintaining relationships between

different family members. This can include someone who helps coordinate communication, mediates conflicts, or serves as a bridge between different branches or generations of the family. The middleman may play a crucial role in fostering and nurturing relationships, ensuring effective communication and cohesion within the family network. Their involvement can help strengthen bonds, promote understanding, and resolve potential misunderstandings or issues that may arise among relatives.

19. Voyaga etgan farzand (adult progeny) refers to the adult offspring or children of an individual. It refers to individuals who have reached adulthood and have grown up under the care and guidance of their parents or guardians.
20. Nikohlamoq (officiate the marriage (nikah) It is the formal event where the marriage contract is solemnized and the couple is officially married according to Islamic traditions. The ceremony usually involves various rituals and customs. It typically includes the exchange of vows, the signing of the marriage contract (nikahnama), the presence of witnesses
21. Oilali qilmoq (have smb start family) is to encourage or inspire someone to start a family, it's important to provide support, guidance and suggestions on how to help someone start a family.
22. Nikohsiz (Unmarried) refers to the state of being unmarried, indicating that an individual has not yet entered into a formal marital union.
23. Nikohda bolmoq (To be married) signifies the status of being married, indicating that an individual is in a legally recognized marital relationship.
24. Voyaga etgan yigit-qiz (Grown-up girl) and (grown-up boy) refer to individuals who have reached a stage of maturity and adulthood. These terms highlight the transition from childhood or adolescence to a more mature stage of life.
25. Oila qurishga undamoq (To aspire to start a family): Oila qurishga undamoq signifies the desire or aspiration to establish a family unit, indicating the intention to enter into a marital relationship and build a household.
26. Er-hotinlik masuliyatlarini ado etish (Fulfilling marital responsibilities): Er-hotinlik masuliyatlarini ado etish refers to fulfilling the rights and

responsibilities that come with being a spouse, including mutual care, support, and fulfilling the duties expected within the marriage.

27. Umr yo'ldoshini tanlash: (Choosing a life partner) Umr yo'ldoshini tanlash means selecting a life partner, indicating the process of seeking and deciding on a suitable spouse with whom to build a lifelong companionship.

28. Munosib kelin tanlash: (Choosing a suitable bride) represents the act of selecting a suitable bride, involving the process of finding a compatible and appropriate match for marriage.

29. Munosib kuyov tanlamoq: (Selecting a suitable groom) refers to the process of choosing a suitable groom, involving the selection of a compatible and appropriate partner for marriage.

Discussion The study on the translation challenges of 29 terms related to family life and marriage in the Uzbek language revealed several key findings. Firstly, the translation of these terms encountered significant challenges due to cultural nuances and linguistic complexities. The terms carried specific connotations, associations, and cultural significance that required careful consideration during the translation process.

Accurate and culturally sensitive translations were found to be crucial in promoting effective cross-cultural communication and understanding. The study highlighted that a mistranslation or an inadequate understanding of these terms could lead to misunderstandings, misinterpretations, and misrepresentations of cultural norms and social practices related to family life and marriage.

1. Moreover, the research underscored the importance of considering the cultural context and social norms associated with these terms. It emphasized the need for translators to possess a deep understanding of the cultural heritage and traditions of Uzbek society to ensure accurate translations that capture the intended meanings and reflect the cultural values.

2. The study also identified areas for further research and exploration in the field of translation studies concerning family life and marriage terms in the Uzbek language. This includes investigating the impact of translation on intercultural

relationships, analyzing the role of gender and power dynamics in the translation process, and examining the influence of globalization and modernization on the translation of traditional family and marriage terms.

3. In conclusion, the study highlighted the significance of accurate and culturally sensitive translations of family life and marriage terms in the Uzbek language. It emphasized the need for translators to navigate the translation challenges posed by cultural nuances and linguistic complexities to promote effective cross-cultural communication and understanding. Further research in this area can contribute to enhancing intercultural dialogue and fostering a deeper appreciation of diverse cultural practices and values.

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